

RESEARCH ARTICLE OPEN ACCESS

High-Resolution Maskless UV Patterning of Vapor Phase Polymerized Conducting Polymer

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Received: 5 May 2025 | **Revised:** 2 June 2025

Funding: This work was supported by the Swedish Foundation for Strategic Research (FID20-0056), European Research Council (Consolidator Grant, 101086683), Knut and Alice Wallenberg Foundation 2019. 0163, Swedish Research Council (VR, 2020-00287), Swedish Government Strategic Research Area in Materials Science on Functional Materials at Linköping University (Faculty Grant SFO-Mat-LiU no. 2009 00971).

Keywords: conducting polymer | electrochromics | maskless lithography | micropatterning | vapor phase polymerization

ABSTRACT

Combining UV radiation with vapor phase polymerization (VPP) enables the fabrication of conducting polymer films with tunable electrical, optical, and electrochemical properties. However, traditional mask-based UV exposure typically requires separation between a photomask and the sample, which limits resolution. This study circumvents this by using a maskless UV exposure system that directly projects high-resolution patterns onto the substrate. Using poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene):toluenesulfonate (PEDOT:Tos) as a model material, the resulting minimum feature sizes are approximately 8 μm —nearly half of what has been achieved using mask-based systems. We find that the obtained resolution is not limited by the optics but is related to material aspects such as molecular diffusion, providing guidelines for further optimizations. Our findings also show that the total delivered dose, rather than exposure time or irradiance, controls the film properties. The resulting PEDOT:Tos patterns exhibit distinct, stable color variations during electrochemical switching, highlighting the potential of maskless UV-VPP for high-resolution electrochromic displays.

1 | Introduction

Conducting polymers (CPs) belong to a fascinating class of materials [1–3] with a diverse range of desirable properties, including flexibility [4], low-cost [5], tunability [6], and biocompatibility [7]. Ongoing research in the patterning of CPs continues to drive their potential applications [8–10]. In this respect, combining UV patterning with vapor phase polymerization (VPP) allows not only topographical patterning but also the modification of multiple material properties in a gradient fashion [11, 12], creating opportunities for new areas of use. VPP is an oxidative polymerization mechanism, and the proposed pathway involves oxidation of monomers such as 3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene (EDOT) to

cation radicals, followed by dimerization, deprotonation, and subsequent doping by anions from the oxidant to form a conjugated polymer network [13]. The kinetics [13–17] of this process is dictated mainly by the oxidant reactivity [18, 19], which can be controlled by adding weak bases [20–22] or block copolymers [23, 24]. Other influential factors include water content [13, 23, 24], monomer volatility [18], polymerization time [25], temperature [15], pressure [26], annealing [27], and washing [28]. Such variation in process and material parameters makes VPP a compelling platform for exploring tunable properties in conducting polymers. When combined with their typically smooth morphology [29], and high conductivity [16, 30–32], and stability [18, 31, 32], this approach has enabled applications such

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as transparent electrodes [33], thermoelectrics [34], transistors [35, 36], smart textiles [37, 38], energy storage [39], sensors [26], and electrochromic displays [40–42].

The UV patterning technique (not to be confused with UV-photolithography patterning) is an emerging concept that utilizes the unique properties of VPP-based polymers. Kim et al. demonstrated that VPP-based PEDOT-methacrylate can lose conductivity through UV-induced crosslinking of methacrylates [43]. In an alternative method described by Edberg et al., UV exposure occurs before the polymerization step, resulting in increased water retention in the exposed region. Increased water retention causes increased deprotonation of EDOT dimers, thus producing PEDOTs with larger thickness, shorter chains and/or conjugation lengths, decreased crystallinity, reduced doping level, and increased roughness in the exposed region. Controlling the UV exposure thereby offers gradient-like variation in conductivity, absorbance, thickness, and ionic mobility [11]. Additionally, Chen et al. reported systematic variations in refractive index [12] for different UV exposures, as used to create tunable structural color images based on PEDOT:toluenesulfonate (PEDOT:Tos) on a metal mirror. In a similar process, Edmunds et al. showed that incorporating highly photoreactive iron salts can inhibit polymerization in UV-exposed areas [44]. The study demonstrated film patterns on flexible substrates through simple surface modification steps; however, this method is not suitable for achieving gradient-like patterns.

As mentioned above, the depositions of highly conducting polymers typically require the use of a block copolymer, such as poly(ethylene glycol)-block-poly(propylene glycol)-block-poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG-PPG-PEG). However, this can make the oxidant layer sticky and limit the UV exposure to be performed in contact mode [11]. Likewise, the oxidant surface tends to be rough, necessitating a substantial distance between the substrate and the mask during the UV exposure step. Reducing the amount of co-block polymer can make the oxidant layer less adhesive [44]. However, this reduction leads to decreased conductivity due to the hydrophilic nature of the oxidants [13, 23, 24]. This leads to a stringent mask-to-substrate requirement which significantly restricts the spatial resolution of the UV-VPP patterning technique, limiting its range of applications. Likewise, this limitation also makes it challenging to determine fundamental resolution limits imposed by other factors, such as molecular diffusion in the oxidant film.

This work circumvents this issue by performing the UV exposure step with a high-resolution maskless system. We evaluate and optimize UV exposure conditions, achieving the smallest features around 8 μm , which is nearly half the size reported in previous studies on UV-VPP patterning [11]. The resolution remains lower than that of a standard photoresist, indicating that limitations are imposed by the material properties rather than by the optics. We demonstrate electrochromic switching properties of the patterns with high stability, exhibiting only minor delamination after 14 h of repeated switching. This work emphasizes UV patterning as a viable concept for applications such as dynamically tunable high-resolution electrochromic displays. The study also implies that further improvement of spatial resolution will require optimization of materials and deposition processes.

2 | Results and Discussion

Figure 1 illustrates the concept of UV-VPP patterning and the difference between the presented approach based on maskless UV illumination (bottom panels) compared to previous reports where exposure was performed through a photomask (top panels). In brief, the UV-VPP process begins by deposition of an oxidant layer on a substrate (step i), UV-exposure (step ii), conversion of monomer to polymer mediated by the oxidant (step iii), and subsequent post-processing such as heat treatment and rinsing steps (step iv). We utilized an established VPP recipe [11] that includes Fe(III):Tos as the oxidant, PEG-PPG-PEG as the block copolymer, and EDOT as the monomer, resulting in patterned PEDOT:Tos films.

2.1 | Comparison of Film Properties Using Mask-Based or Maskless UV Exposure

To illustrate the importance of the separation between photomask and substrate for conventional UV-VPP patterning, we quantify the loss in spatial resolution for different separations for a 50 μm line. The resolution loss is here defined as the linewidth deviation calculated as half the difference between the designed (Figure 1ii) and measured line widths (Figure 1v). As expected, the polymer patterns were wider than the designed pattern, and the linewidth deviation significantly increased with separation distance (Figure 2a). Because the spin-coated oxidant and block copolymer stick to the mask if in physical contact (Figure S1), this highlights the need for a maskless exposure system that projects the UV pattern onto the oxidant at high resolution without requiring contact. Indeed, the initial results shown in Figure 2b indicate significantly lower linewidth deviation when the same pattern was exposed using a maskless system.

Adapting the concept for maskless exposure requires considering differences from the traditional mask-based systems, such as irradiance and emission wavelengths. While previous studies clarified that both exposure time and irradiance can affect the final film properties [11, 12], their separate roles and total dose (energy per unit area) were not examined in detail. Figure 2c presents the thickness and electrical conductivity of PEDOT:Tos films that were obtained using the traditional exposure system at different irradiances and exposure times but with a fixed dose of roughly 2000 mJ cm^{-2} . All exposed samples showed significantly lower conductivity and higher thickness than unexposed samples (i.e., 0 mW cm^{-2} intensity, presented at the far left). The thicknesses of the exposed samples were within a range of 224–234 nm, in contrast to 196–205 nm for the unexposed samples. Conductivity values for the exposed samples were 9–26 S cm^{-1} , whereas unexposed samples exhibited values in the range 480–590 S cm^{-1} . We, therefore, conclude that films produced under various combinations of irradiance and exposure show nearly identical properties (i.e., equal modulation) when the total dose is kept constant. The same conclusion can also be drawn from UV-vis-NIR absorbance data (Figure S2) and also holds for different experimental conditions (Figure S3).

Figure 2d presents thickness values for different films produced after exposure to various doses using the mask-based or maskless systems. The maskless system shows essentially the same

FIGURE 1 | Schematic of UV-VPP patterning using traditional (top) or maskless (bottom) UV light exposure: (i) preparation of the substrate with a layer of oxidant and block copolymer (Fe(III):Tos and PEG-PPG-PEG), (ii) UV light exposure of the oxidant through a mask (top) or using a mask-less system (bottom), (iii) polymerization of PEDOT:Tos from EDOT monomers in a chamber with controlled temperature and pressure, and (iv) post-processing through annealing and washing of the polymerized film. (v) The right-most part illustrates the final patterned structures and anticipated differences between mask-based and mask-less patterning.

thicknesses and modulation compared to the traditional mask-based approach. For example, both systems exhibit around a 60 nm increase in film thickness for a dose of 4200 mJ cm^{-2} compared to unexposed samples. These results are not trivial considering the spectral differences between the two systems, where the doses for the mask-based system include contributions from two peaks at 365 nm (i-line) and 405 nm (h-line), while the dose for the maskless system originates from one emission peak at 390 nm. We note in this respect that the fraction of the UV light that is absorbed is similar for the two systems despite the spectral differences, as examined by also accounting for the wavelength-dependent absorption by the oxidant (Note S1, Figures S4 and S5). Hence, the results are in agreement with the absorbed dose being the determining factor for the modulation strength. Figure 2f,g present UV-vis absorbance spectra of the same films. The results are similar for the mask-based and maskless exposures, including a gradually increasing absorbance around the 400 nm dip, which can be attributed to increase in short-chain PEDOT:Tos and/or shorter conjugation lengths [11]. For the same dose of 4200 mJ cm^{-2} , both the mask-based and maskless systems exhibited approximately a 10% increase at 400 nm compared to an unexposed sample.

2.2 | Maskless UV-VPP Patterning and Resolution Limits

To investigate possibilities and limitations in terms of maskless UV-VPP patterning, we exposed oxidants in 1–5 μm wide UV stripes with various doses. Figure 3a,b show microscope images of two such PEDOT:Tos samples where the oxidants were exposed to 2100 and 8400 mJ cm^{-2} , respectively. Both the low and high exposure doses could successfully induce micropatterns with high resolution. We also note that the patterns generally show larger linewidths compared to the designs. For instance, the pattern widths for the 2 μm design are $\sim 8 \mu\text{m}$ for the lower dose, and $15 \mu\text{m}$ for the higher dose (see insets). This corresponds to a linewidth deviation of ~ 3 and $\sim 6.5 \mu\text{m}$, for 2100 and 8400 mJ cm^{-2}

doses, respectively. Figure 2c shows the linewidth deviations for all tested exposures and designs, indicating that the linewidth deviation not only increases with exposure dose but also scales with the design that was exposed. The trend is also consistent across multiple substrates (Figure S6). Moreover, we did not observe clear patterns for small design-dose combinations (e.g., 700 mJ cm^{-2} dose, 1 μm design), but we could observe patterns for the same low dose for larger designed linewidths. It could be that such conditions resulted in contrasts between unexposed and exposed areas that were not detectable by our microscope. Another plausible explanation is that the combination of low dose and small linewidth did not result in any pattern. Previous reports indeed mentioned that there were no discernible patterns below a minimum oxidant concentration [44], and it is known that the oxidant reactivity increases with increasing dose [11]. The absence of visible patterns for small linewidths and low doses in our experiment could be due to insufficient locally affected oxidant, likely in combination with microscale polymerization dynamics and/or oxidant diffusion between exposure and polymerization. Previous findings showed that the oxidant and block copolymer tend to diffuse (for example, to fill a gap created through needle striping) [45], which could potentially also result in pattern deviation. To test if diffusion or other post-exposure effects could be involved in causing the linewidth deviation, we deliberately introduced a time delay between the UV exposure and the polymerization steps (Figure 1(ii),(iii)). The results show a clear increase in linewidth deviation with increasing time delay (Figure 2d,e). We further note that diffusion may also take place during the polymerization step (30 min), which is in accordance with a remaining linewidth deviation also for no deliberate time delays (Figure 2e). The difference between different exposure doses may be related to increased molecular diffusion coefficient in the oxidant upon UV exposure, as previously investigated by impedance spectroscopy [11]. Other effects, such as increased light scattering at higher doses, may also be involved. However, we could consistently achieve better resolution (close to zero linewidth deviation) with conventional photoresists (Figure S7).

FIGURE 2 | (a) Loss in patterning resolution for different mask-to-substrate distances (5.5 mW cm^{-2} i-line with 127 s exposure time, or roughly 1000 mJ cm^{-2} wideband UV dose, see Methods section). (b) Patterns on PEDOT:Tos films that are produced through a mask-based (top, best case tested) and maskless system (bottom) with $\sim 1000 \text{ mJ cm}^{-2}$. The dashed squares represent an unexposed region of $200 \times 50 \mu\text{m}$. (c) Conductivity and thickness modulation (average of three) of different PEDOT:Tos films where oxidants were exposed to similar doses ($\sim 2000 \text{ mJ cm}^{-2}$) by adjusting exposure time and intensity (top and bottom axes). For comparison, the datapoints on the left of the axis break represent unexposed samples. (d) Thickness modulation of final films (average of three) where oxidants were exposed to different doses with a maskless and mask-based system. (e, f) Absorbance of films exposed to various doses using a mask-based and maskless system, respectively.

2.3 | Electrochromic Switching Behavior

An important aspect of PEDOT and other conducting polymers is their electrochromic switching capability [46]. In brief, PEDOT has a deep blue color in its reduced neutral state due to bandgap absorption at around 600 nm. Introducing charges by oxidation suppresses this absorption band and introduces optical features in the near-infrared and infrared regions related to charged polarons and bipolarons. The material, therefore, attains lower visible light absorption upon oxidation, which produces a bleached or transparent appearance. This process is reversible, such that reducing the PEDOT again will lead to the reappearance of the visible absorption and deep blue color [45, 47]. Interestingly, conducting polymers made through UV-VPP attain electrochromic behavior that gradually varies with the local UV exposure dose. This feature has been used to create dynamic greyscale and structurally colored images as well as switchable thermal images [12, 40–42, 48]. To explore the possibility of UV-VPP patterning for high-resolution electrochromic displays, we here report the electrochromic properties and stability of polymers produced through our maskless UV-VPP patterning approach. As illustrated in Figure 4a, the experimental setup allows simultaneous tracking of micrographs, spectra, and chronoamperometric behavior. Figure 4b shows micrographs at nine different voltage biases for two $\sim 8 \mu\text{m}$ wide lines patterned with 2100 mJ cm^{-2} UV dose for. Both the exposed and non-exposed regions show electrochromic switching, and to varying extents as expected [40]

and evaluated in more detail below. The thin patterned lines show good stability and no visible degradation after $\sim 1 \text{ h}$ of 50 CV cycles and with an additional $\sim 1 \text{ h}$ of switching between various static voltages (Figure 4c). To better understand film stability, continuous chronoamperometric and spectroscopic data were acquired from larger patterns (i.e., from patterns that the spectrometer can resolve) exposed to $\sim 1000 \text{ mJ cm}^{-2}$ dose (see Figure S8 for cyclic voltammetry data). Figure 4d shows the chronoamperometric data during the 1st, 2nd, 29th, and 30th cycles, where each cycle lasted 60 s comprising four voltage biases. Only minor current changes are observed during the first two cycles, after which the current values remain consistent through the 30-min-long measurement. High stability is also confirmed from spectra taken at the most oxidized and reduced states during the initial and final cycle (Figure 4e). Prolonged switching measurements over 14 h showed signs of delamination (Figure S9). However, this delamination was initiated close to the edges of the substrate and not due to the UV-patterning itself. Therefore, we foresee that improving surface adhesion may generate yet higher stability.

We finally compare electrochromic absorbance spectra for PEDOT:Tos films made using 0 (Figure 4f), 700 (Figure 4g) and (Figure 4h) 4200 mJ cm^{-2} UV exposure doses. Micrographs of the most oxidized (0.8 V) and reduced (-0.8 V) states are provided as insets. We first note that the general optical variation upon redox-tuning is the same for all films and in line with the

FIGURE 3 | (a,b) Micrographs showing patterns on PEDOT:Tos films where oxidant layers were UV-exposed in $1\text{--}5 \mu\text{m}$ wide stripes with 2100 and 8400 mJ cm^{-2} doses, respectively. Please note the difference between the design identifiers (in white) and the micrograph scales (in pink). The insets depict the resulting pattern widths corresponding to a design width of $2 \mu\text{m}$. (c) Linewidth deviation for different pattern designs and exposure doses. (d) Micrographs of $10 \mu\text{m}$ designed lines made without time delay (top) and with 60 min time delay (bottom) for two different exposure doses. (e) Linewidth deviations (average of two) for $10 \mu\text{m}$ designed lines for various time delays.

general description of PEDOT electrochromism, with a neutral absorption peak around 600 nm appearing in the reduced state and disappearing when oxidizing the material, accompanied by increased absorbance in the near-infrared region. The results further indicate that the electrochromic modulation range decreases with increasing UV exposure dose, which agrees with the observations for the thin lines (Figure 4b). Brooke et al. reported similar findings for mask-based UV patterning [40], for which decreased polymer capacitance indicated reduced doping modulation in UV-exposed regions. Moreover, the films in the UV-exposed regions show increased surface roughness [11], which may also affect the color contrast [49]. We finally note that the most significant color shifts occur around the 0 V bias points for both exposed and non-exposed films (Figure 4f–h). Thus, UV-VPP patterned PEDOT:Tos can act as electrochromic display devices where the voltage source could be a thermal or piezoelectric energy harvester, i.e., an on-demand battery-less display.

3 | Conclusions

This work adopted the UV-induced patterning of VPP-based polymers with a high-resolution maskless system, circumventing the previously reported mask-to-substrate distance constraints and producing patterned lines with a linewidth deviation of almost half of the previous mask-based approach. In addition, this approach has the advantage of enabling simple modification of pattern design without the need to make a new photomask.

We demonstrated that switching to a maskless system in the context of UV-VPP is not trivial and requires careful reconsideration of exposure conditions such as spectral emission of the light source and spectral absorbance of the oxidant layer. We anticipate that the required irradiated dose could be lowered by jointly optimizing these two parameters, for example, by adopting UV light sources with lower wavelengths for which the oxidant provides higher absorbance (Figure S4). Crucially, we showed that the pattern resolution of a maskless system is dictated not only by the optics but also by material and process parameters such as molecular diffusion and other post-exposure delay effects. Future work may focus on further understanding and mitigating the effects of such material-related processes. The study highlights UV-VPP patterning as a robust technique with applications in high-resolution electrochromic displays as well as for novel applications such as gradient doping and ionic mobility that remain unexplored. We believe that the insights gleaned from our work will elucidate potential limitations and optimization strategies, encouraging further investigation into bottom-up VPP polymer patterning.

4 | Experimental Section

4.1 | Materials

Clevios CB 54 V2 (54% wt/wt Fe(III) p-toluenesulfonate (Tosylate) in butanol) was purchased from Heraeus. The monomer

FIGURE 4 | (a) Schematic of the electrochemical setup. (b) Micrographs (transmission mode) showing the electrochromic behavior of PEDOT:Tos for two 8 μm patterned lines (2100 mJ cm^{-2}). (c) Micrographs of the same lines as in panel (b) before (top) and after (bottom) ~ 2 h of switching. (d) Chronoamperometry data during 30 min of continuous cycling of a film patterned with 1000 mJ cm^{-2} dose (for selected cycles as indicated). (e) Absorbance spectra of the same film at 0.8 V (oxidized) and -0.8 V (reduced) recorded during cycle 1 and 30 of the chronoamperometric switching. (f–h) Absorption spectra of films where the oxidant was exposed to 0, 700, 4200 mJ cm^{-2} UV doses, respectively. The micrographs in the insets show films $600 \times 600 \mu\text{m}$ in their most reduced and oxidized states. The blue to pink gradients represent 0.2 V steps.

EDOT ($142.18 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$) and the triblock copolymer PEG-PPG-PEG (avg. 5800 g mol^{-1}) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Solvents 1-butanol and ethanol were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and Solveco, respectively. The CB 54 V2 was diluted to 40% wt/wt Fe(III) p-toluenesulfonate (Tosylate) in butanol. All other chemicals were used without further purification or modification.

4.2 | Vapor Phase Polymerization (VPP)

The PEDOT:Tos films were deposited by the VPP process, according to a previous report [11]. Standard microscope glass slides were cut into $25 \times 25 \text{ mm}$ and ultrasonicated in Hellmanex 2% in deionized water, acetone, and isopropanol, respectively (15 min for each step). The glass was further cleaned with oxygen

plasma at 200 W for 5 min and kept in a sealed box overnight. The oxidant mixture was prepared by combining 2 g 40% wt/wt Fe(III) p-toluenesulfonate (Tosylate) in butanol, 1.5 g of PEG-PPG-PEG (avg. 5800 g mol^{-1}), and 3 g of 99.7% ethanol. This resulted in an oxidant solution where the weight percentage of Fe(III) p-toluenesulfonate, PEG-PPG-PEG, butanol, and ethanol are 12.3%, 23.08%, 18.46%, and 46.15%, respectively. In the VPP step, the oxidant mixture was first spin-coated (1500 rpm, 30 s) and subsequently dried on a hot plate at 70°C for 30 s. The spin-coated substrate was then illuminated with various patterns of varying UV doses using a mask aligner (MA6, SÜSS MicroTec) or a maskless system (μMLA , Heidelberg Instruments Mikrotechnik). The substrate with UV-exposed oxidant was immediately transferred to a vacuum desiccator (50°C , 70 mbar, J.P Selecta) that was previously filled with 200 μL EDOT. The substrate was kept in the desiccator for 30 min (i.e., polymerization time).

After polymerization, the substrate was again annealed on a hotplate at 70 °C for 2 min and subsequently rinsed carefully in 99.7% ethanol. Thus, PEDOT:Tos films with various patterns were obtained. All fabrication steps were performed in a class 1000 yellow light environment.

4.3 | UV Sources and Dose Measurement

The lamp for the mask-based system is a high-pressure mercury vapor lamp (prominent peaks at 365 and 405 nm in the UV range). Irradiances for these peaks were read from the CIC1200 controller as i-line (detector range 345–385 nm) and h-line (detector range 345–460 nm). However, for most of the study, the integrated UV doses were measured with AKTIPRINT UV-integrator (full-UV, 250–410 nm range), which captures total energy across a wide spectral range. When estimating the actual absorbed dose by the material, this measurement was later weighted by the absorbance spectra of the components. Emission spectra were obtained using CCS200/M (ThorLabs) (see Note S1 for details).

The maskless system employs a high-intensity UV-LED operating with a peak at 390 nm. The LED power remained stable, with no drop greater than 1% throughout the reporting period. Consistent modulation results across different doses indicate that the dose values derived from the instrument software (as calibrated by the manufacturer) are reliable across multiple substrates.

4.4 | Spectroelectrochemical Characterization

The spectroelectrochemical characterization was carried out using a specially designed electrochemical cell (Back microscopy EFC, Redox.me) set up in a three-electrode configuration (see Figure 4a). The substrate was positioned at the bottom of the cell, with the film immersed in 0.1 M KCl in deionized water. The electrodes were connected to a potentiostat (Autolab PGSTAT204, Metrohm), employing a Ag/AgCl reference electrode, a platinum coil as the counter electrode, and the PEDOT:Tos sample as the working electrode. The electrochemical cell was placed under a microscope (Nikon Eclipse L2000N) equipped with a beam splitter (SM1CP2, ThorLabs). The substrate was illuminated from below, with part of the transmitted light directed to a camera (Infinity 1, Lumenera), while the remainder was channeled to a spectrophotometer (QePRO, OceanOptics) via a 200 µm diameter optical fiber (Thorlabs). This arrangement enables simultaneous monitoring of electrochemical, spectral (absorbance/transmittance), and micrographic data. All comparative micrographs were captured under identical imaging conditions and without any post-processing, aside from rotation and cropping. Slight fluctuations were noted in the absorbance spectra during prolonged equipment operation. We speculate that these variations arise from the non-cooled illuminating light sources, as similar fluctuations were also observed on bare glass substrates (Figure S10).

4.5 | Profilometry

Thickness measurements were performed using a profilometer (Dektak XT, Bruker) with 0.3 mg stylus force. No scratching or

deterioration of the films was observed. The scan resolution was 0.033 µm for most samples.

4.6 | Conductivity Measurements

Sheet resistance data were taken with a four-point probe system (Oscilla). An average of 10 data points were taken with a 0.1 V increment. The target voltage and currents were adjusted depending on film conductivity. Between successive measurements, the tips were cleaned with isopropanol. Conductivities were then calculated from sheet resistance and thickness.

4.7 | UV-Vis-NIR Measurements

UV-vis-NIR spectra were acquired with a Lambda 900 spectrometer (Perkin Elmer) (300–2000 nm with 5 nm resolution for films and 420–200 nm with 10 nm resolution for oxidant samples).

4.8 | Linewidth Measurements

Linewidths were determined with ImageJ (Wayne Rasband and contributors) from micrographs calibrated against known dimensions.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge support from the Swedish Foundation for Strategic Research (FID20-0056), European Research Council (Consolidator Grant, 101086683), the Knut and Alice Wallenberg Foundation (Wallenberg Academy Fellow, 2019. 0163), the Swedish Research Council (VR, 2020-00287), and the Swedish Government Strategic Research Area in Materials Science on Functional Materials at Linköping University (Faculty Grant SFO-Mat-LiU No. 2009 00971).

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings in this study are openly available in Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15532559>.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.

Supporting File 1: mame70045-sup-0001-SuppMat.pdf.